

2D Stacking of graphene and boron nitride for efficient metal free overall water splitting

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Abstract

Constructing bifunctional electrocatalysts is essential for efficient water splitting. Rational interface engineering is an effective method for modifying active sites and promoting electronic charge transfer, resulting in improved water splitting efficiency. In this study, we designed a metal-free, 2D structure of graphene and boron nitride (h-BN). 2D stacking of two different layers generated abundant interfaces as well as huge electrochemical active sites. As a result, the graphene/h-BN stacked structure has a very low overpotential of 28 mV (for 10 mA/cm² current density) for hydrogen evolution. At the same time, a significantly low overpotential of 360 mV (for 50 mA/cm² current density) was achieved for oxygen evolution. The stacked structure of graphene/h-BN has been effectively utilized as a promising cathode and anode in a two-electrode system for accomplishing overall water splitting. Thus, our investigation suggests that rational construction of heterogeneous interfaces by stacking different 2D nanostructures can accelerate the overall water splitting by maximizing the electrochemical performance.

Keywords: Overall water splitting, 2D stacking, Graphene, Interface, Metal-free, Electrocatalyst

1. Introduction

Water splitting is a process by which water is separated into its constituent elements, hydrogen and oxygen.[1–4] This process has gained significant attention in recent years due to the potential of hydrogen as a renewable and clean fuel source.[5,6] Hydrogen can be used in fuel cells to generate electricity with water as the only by-product, making it an attractive alternative to fossil fuels.[1–4] However, the current methods for hydrogen production rely on fossil fuels, which are not sustainable and contribute to global warming. Therefore, the development of an efficient and sustainable method for water splitting is critical to meet the energy needs of the future.[4,6]

Water splitting is a complex electrochemical process that requires the presence of a suitable electrocatalyst to lower the activation energy and facilitate the reaction.[7,8] The overall reaction requires a minimum of 1.23 V of energy to occur, which is known as the thermodynamic potential of water splitting.[1,8] However, in practice, a higher voltage is required due to various losses in the system, including overpotentials, ohmic losses, and kinetic limitations.[1,6] Therefore, the development of efficient and stable water splitting electrocatalysts is crucial to overcome these challenges and improve the overall performance of the system. In recent years, significant progress has been made in the development of water splitting electrocatalysts, driven by the increasing demand for renewable energy sources and the need to mitigate climate change.[4,6,9,10] This progress has been achieved through the use of various strategies, including the design of new materials, the optimization of their structures, and the use of advanced characterization techniques to understand their properties and performance.[4,6] There is a substantial emphasis on creating bifunctional electrocatalysts that have the ability to catalyze both the HER and OER in an alkaline environment, thereby improving the efficiency of water splitting as a whole.[11,12] In this respect, designing bifunctional electrocatalysts by integrating materials that are active towards both HER and OER is an effective strategy.[12,13]

In recent years, two-dimensional (2D) stacked materials have emerged as promising candidates for efficient electrocatalysis in water splitting.[14–16] 2D stacked materials have a unique layered structure, with strong covalent bonds within the layers and weak van der Waals forces between the layers.[15,17–19] This structure results in several advantageous properties, including high surface area, high conductivity, and tunable electronic and catalytic properties.[14,15,17,20] And among the various 2D structures, Graphene-based materials have gained significant attention as the catalysis field due to their intrinsic properties and have demonstrated particular promise in water electrolytic applications among various 2D materials.[21–25] Graphene is a nanosheet composed of carbon(C) atoms arranged in a hexagonal pattern, which boasts exceptional properties such as exceptional electrical conductivity, impressive mechanical robustness, and an incredibly large theoretical surface area.[21,26,27] Due to the unique arrangement of sp^2 carbon atoms bonded through three sigma (σ) bonds with adjacent carbon atoms, electronic characteristics and reaction kinetics of graphene can be tuned by doping and forming heterostructure.[26–28]

Here in the present work, electronic structure and reaction kinetics of graphene was modified by doping and forming 2D stacked heterostructure. For doping, boron (B) and nitrogen (N) atoms replaced the C atoms of graphene. On the other hand, 2D heterostructure was formed by stacking hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) with the graphene layer. Due to the creation of abundant interfaces as the result of graphene and h-BN stacking hydrogen adsorption at the electrode surface significantly increased. 2D graphene/h-BN stacked structured possess very low overpotential (28 mV at 10 mA/cm²) for cathodic polarization. At the same time, very low anodic overpotential of

360 mV (for 50 10 mA/cm²) ensured 2D stacked graphene/h-BN as a potential material for overall water splitting application.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Reagents. Natural graphite flakes were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid, potassium Permanganate, hydrogen peroxide, Boric acid, Ammonia solution, N, N-dimethyl formamide (DMF) and potassium hydroxide were purchased from Merck, Mumbai, India. Conducting carbon black (EC-600JD, purity: >95%) and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) were purchased from Akzo Nobel Amides Co., Ltd, South Korea. Nickel foam was purchased from Shanghai Winfay New Material Co., Ltd., China.

2.2 Synthesis procedure. Graphene oxide (GO) was prepared from natural graphite flake according to the modified Hummers method. Three different samples was prepared by annealing method. For that, 0.4g boric acid, 0.4 g urea, and different quantity of GO was ground into homogeneous form and transfer in to a porcelain crucible. The mixture was annealed by keeping the crucible at 650 °C for 4 h under Ar atmosphere. Then the mixture was collected and cooled at room temperature. Then the product was washed several times with distilled water until the pH was neutral. Finally, the product was dried overnight at 100 °C inside a vacuum oven. 1st product, h-BN was prepared without GO, and the sample was designated as G0BN. 2D stacking of graphene and h-BN was prepared by using 0.4 g GO, and the sample was designated as G0.4BN. Another sample with higher graphene content was prepared by using 0.8 g GO, and the sample was designated as G0.8BN.

2.3 Characterization. X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies of the composite were carried out at room temperature on a D/Max 2500 V/PC (Rigaku Corporation) at a scan rate of 1° min⁻¹ (Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 0.15418$ nm). Raman spectroscopy was recorded a Witec alpha300 R using a laser wavelength of 532 nm. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) images were recorded with Sigma HD, Carl Zeiss, Germany. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images were recorded using JEOL JEM-2100 FS. The electrical conductivity was measured using a four probe set up with a KEITHLEY delta system consisting of an AC and DC current source (model: 6221) and a Nanovoltmeter (model: 2182A). Electrochemical measurements were carried out with a PARSTAT 4000 (Princeton Applied Research, USA. The cyclic voltammetry (CV), linear sweep voltammetry, Tafel plot, and the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were carried out in 1 M aqueous KOH electrolyte (room temperature). HER and OER properties were measured at three electrode system, where Pt and Ag/AgCl were used as counter and reference electrodes. Working electrodes were prepared on a FTO glass slide. Samples were dispersed in DMF with 5% PVDF as additive. Dispersions was drop-casted on the FTO glass and dried at 70 °C for overnight. Bare parts of FTO was covered by non-conductive resin to ensured that the FTO glass did not take part in the electrochemical reactions. Two electrode system was employed for the overall water splitting measurement.

3. Results and discussions

FE-SEM and TEM images were captured to confirm the formation of a 2D structure as well as the stacking of graphene and h-BN layers. **Figure 1a** shows the FE-SEM of G0.4BN. A lot of 2D multi-layered flakes of different aspect ratios were shown in Figure 1a. At the same time, layer-by-layer stacking was also noticed. TEM image (**Figure 1b**) shows the presence of almost transparent as well as overlapped layered structures. However, the presence of h-BN and graphene

could not be identified from the TEM image. To investigate the components, HR-TEM (**Figure 1c**) was captured in the overlapping region and the d-spacing was calculated. The d-spacing of graphene and h-BN is 0.333 and 0.335 nm, respectively. Two different regions (A and B) were selected in the HR-TEM images. The d-spacing was measured as ~ 0.333 (similar to h-BN) and 0.335 nm (similar to graphene), corresponding to regions A and B, respectively.[29] The presence of two different layers of different d-spacing suggested the stacking of two different components, h-BN and graphene. The stacking of two different layers with different lattice parameters, was confirmed by the selected area diffraction pattern (SAED) of G0.4BN (**Figure 1d**). Generally, for pure graphene and h-BN, a ring containing six bright diffraction spots is found in the SAED patterns. However, in the present case, some of the bright spots were due to the overlapping of two spots corresponding to the two different 2D structures with almost the same lattice parameter. Here the d-spacing was calculated from the SAED pattern (**Figure 1e**), which corresponds to the four lines drawn along the bright spots: D, H, F, and B. The d-spacing was found to be 0.33, 0.331, 0.335, and 0.33, corresponding to the D, H, F, and B lines of the SAED pattern. The d-spacing calculated from the SAED pattern completely agreed with the HR-TEM analysis. On the other hand, HR-TEM was also captured along the edge of the h-BN/rGO stacked layers (**Figure 1f**). The HR-TEM shows the presence of AB stacking of hexagonal structures. Line spacing at the edge of the 2D layer was clearly visible from the HR-TEM image. The FFT pattern was generated from the HR-TEM image and is represented in Figure 1f. For pure graphene and h-BN, the FFT pattern predicts the appearance of six bright spots corresponding to the aromatic and hexagonal rings. However, in the present case, twelve bright spots were shown in the FFT pattern, which confirms the stacking of two different 2D layers in G0.4BN.

Figure 1. Structural and morphological analysis (a) FE-SEM, (b) TEM, (c) HR-TEM, (d) SAED pattern, (e) corresponding d-spacing, (f) HR-TEM, and (g) corresponding FFT of G0.4BN

Figure S1a (FE-SEM of G0BN) shows that annealing of boric acid and urea (without graphene oxide) formed large particles of h-BN with hexagonal structure. Similar morphology was achieved from TEM analysis (**Figure S1b**). The edge of the particle of G0BN has hexagonal structure. On

the other hand, FE-SEM image (**Figure S1c**) ensured that G0.8BN has sheet like morphology. Due to the higher amount of GO in the precursor and lower content of urea and boric acid, h-BN was not formed during synthesis. B and N were doped in the reduced graphene (rGO). TEM image (**Figure S1d**) of G0.8BN also shows the presence of almost transparent graphene sheets.

Figure 2a shows the UV-vis absorption of G0.4BN and G0.8BN. G0.8BN shows the characteristic graphene peak at ~280 nm, which corresponds to the resonant excitonic effects of electron-hole interaction in the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition.[20,27,30] No separate peak for h-BN was observed for G0.8BN. However, a shift in the peak position was noticed for G0.4BN. G0.4BN shows two absorption peaks at 263 and 333 nm, respectively. The peak at the lower wavelength is due to the overlapping of two peaks of $\pi-\pi^*$ inter-band transition of h-BN and π -plasmon absorption of graphene.[27,30] The 2nd absorption peak confirms the 2D stacking of graphene and the h-BN layer. The peak at higher wavelength is due to the intermediate structure formed due to the alternate arrangement of graphene and h-BN.[20,27,31] **Figure S2** of the supporting information shows the XRD of the samples. XRD of h-BN/rGO stacked structure was compared with pure rGO, and pure h-BN. Although an intense peak was observed for the sample without graphene, doped and 2D stacked samples show broadened peaks. These peaks can be attributed to the (002) plane for bare h-BN.[27] Similarly, rGO also shows the (002) peak at ~25° which agreed with the previous published results.[32–34] On the other hand, a little shift of the XRD (002) peaks towards a higher angle was due to the insertion of B, N, and the stacking of two different layers. The broadened peaks also appeared due to the stacking and doping effects. The UV-vis and XRD studies suggested that while 2D stacked structures were formed when lower GO content was used during synthesis, B and N were doped within the graphene layer when GO content was higher during the annealing process. Figure 2b shows the temperature-dependent electrical conductivity plots of different 2D samples. The presence of a foreign element as well as stacking significantly influenced the electrical conductivity. Wide-band gap h-BN (G0BN) is electrically non-conductive, while graphene is a highly conductive material. As a result, G0BN does not show significant variation with temperature. The samples with graphene exhibited high electrical conductivity.

While measuring the electrical conductivity of G0.4BN, there is a formation of conductive graphene channels within the h-BN. Yu et al. studied the effect of hybridization of graphene and h-BN layers and found that the electronic properties of the graphene layers remained unaffected in spite of the presence of h-BN.[35] In the present study, at a particular stoichiometry, graphene layers were embedded between h-BN layers. As a result, an electrically conducting path was formed.[27] Similar results were obtained by Wei et al., where they reported that the B atom in a BN monolayer could be replaced with C atom doping, which results in n-type conductivity.[36] The altered electrical conductivity of G0.4BN can be explained in terms of band gap energy or UV-vis absorbance.[37] UV-vis peak of G0.4BN is completely different than graphene, graphene oxide, and h-BN. The band gap of h-BN was modified significantly after forming superlattice kind of structure as the result of hybridization of graphene and h-BN layers.[20,37] On the other hand, due to the presence of a higher amount of GO during the synthesis of G0.8BN, N- and B-doped doped-graphene was formed. It was interesting to notice that the electrical conductivity of G0.8BN was much higher than rGO. Similar results were reported by several researchers.[38–40] Due to the presence of π -electronic conjugated network, the electrical conductivity of G0.8BN increased significantly. In addition, after doping, the pyrrolic-N bonding configuration became the dominant factor in rGO, which enhanced the π -bond in carbon atoms and formed percolation ways for

electron conduction. As a result, doped rGO shows higher electrical conductivity than un-doped rGO.

However, the nature of the temperature dependence was quite interesting. A linear characteristic was noticed for rGO with an average electrical conductivity of 540 s/m. On the other hand, conductivity increased significantly for the doped sample (G0.8BN). At the low temperature region (300 to 330 K), the electrical conductivity did not increase, but at the higher temperature region, the electrical conductivity of G0.8BN reached to ~750 s/m (at 380 K). On the other hand, the 2D stacked sample (G0.4BN) shows a sharp increase in electrical conductivity from 300 to 380 K (from 535 to 645 s/m). The electrical conductivity profile suggested that both the stacked and doped samples have n-type semiconducting nature.

Figure 2 (a) UV-vis absorption of G0.4BN, (b) electrical conductivity vs. temperature plots, high resolution Raman spectroscopy (c) G and D peak, and (d) 2D peak of G0.4BN.

Raman spectroscopy is important for quantifying defects in graphene and its derivatives, which comprise sp^2 carbon structures. Electrical conductivity measurement shows that, in spite of the presence of non-conducting 2D h-BN sandwiched between graphene layers, its electron mobility was not hampered. Generally, two major Raman peaks are observed in graphene. One peak appears around 1580 cm^{-1} , known as the G peak, due to the high frequency E_{2g} optical phonon of graphite or nano-crystalline graphite.[41–43] The bond stretching of sp^2 carbon atoms in the hexagonal ring

is responsible for the G peak. Another peak appears around $\sim 1335\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to the defective nanocrystalline graphite. This peak is called the D peak and is related to the A_{1g} breathing modes of sp^2 carbon atoms in rings.[44] Here, G0.4BN shows a sharp G peak with a broad D band spectrum at 1579 and 1337 cm^{-1} , respectively (**Figure 2c**). To understand the broadened peak profile, the G and D peaks were fitted using five deconvoluted peaks (G, D, D', D*, and D'') using Lorentzian functions.[45,46] The D'' band at 1450 cm^{-1} , corresponds to the presence of an amorphous phase within the crystalline graphene. In the present case, due to the presence of the alternate h-BN layer, an intense D'' peak was noticed. As confirmed from the UV-vis absorption, a graphene/h-BN edge is present in G0.4BN, and the appearance of a sharp D'' peak further confirmed the stacking of two different 2D materials.[47] Another validation of the presence of h-BN within graphene was found due to the appearance of the D* band at 1250 cm^{-1} which was originated from the sp^3 -rich phases within the sp^2 structure.[48] However, the D' band intensity at 1610 cm^{-1} is quite low. D' band is related to the amount of impurities in graphene, and here, due to the complete reduction of GO during the annealing process, the low intensity peak was observed. **Figure 2d** shows the deconvoluted 2D peak of G0.4BN. A 2D peak appeared at $\sim 2680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and is due to the second order of zone-boundary phonons. In graphene, the 2D peak is related to the combination of opposite momentum phonons, and no defect is required for the activation of this peak. Thus, various information related to the carrier mobility and layered structure of graphene can be gained by analyzing the 2D peak.[41] Here, the 2D peak is quite broad in nature due to the stacking of h-BN and graphene. At the same time, it was found that six Lorentzian deconvoluted peaks with almost the same full width half maxima (FWHM) of $\sim 30\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are required to fit the 2D peak of G0.4BN. Thus, it can be concluded that at least three layers of graphene and h-BN were stacked with each other in G0.4BN.[49]

In order to investigate the electrochemical behaviour, CV of the samples were captured at a 10 mV/s scan rate with a wide potential range. **Figure S3** of the supporting information shows that pure h-BN (G0BN) has a redox nature with a comparatively small current response. The CV of G0BN is stable within the potential range of ~ -0.4 to 1.6 V , and beyond the potential polarization was noticed. However, the stable window of CV was significantly decreased for the 2D stacked graphene/h-BN structure (**Figure S4**), ensuring earlier polarization. G0.4BN shows a potential window of ~ 0 to 1.45 V . G0.4BN also possess redox behaviour similar like pure h-BN. However, the current response of G0.4BN is much higher in comparison to G0BN. At the same time, pure h-BN has almost zero response after the reduction peak (after 0.75 V), but G0.4BN possesses current response like an electrochemical double layer (EDLC) up to 0 V . This CV nature ensured that even after reduction occurred, there was adsorption of hydrogen on the electrode surface. The interfacial effect of graphene and h-BN was the reason for such adsorption property of G0.4BN. On the other hand, the CV of G0.8BN shows an almost EDLC nature with a potential window of ~ -0.1 to 1.6 V (**Figure S5**).

The origin of EDLC in rGO or graphene lies in the electrostatic accumulation of free charges on the surface of carbonaceous materials. On the other hand, redox reactions occur due to the presence of a band gap energy in semiconducting materials.[27,50,51] The position of the Fermi level in a semiconductor plays a crucial role in facilitating redox charge transfer between the electrode and electrolyte. If the redox potential of the electrolyte falls below the energy level of the Fermi band, charge is transferred from the electrode to the electrolyte. Conversely, if the redox potential of the electrolyte exceeds the energy level of the Fermi band, charge is transferred from the electrolyte

to the electrode. This type of charge transfer occurs at a specific applied potential when equilibrium is achieved between the electrode and electrolyte, known as the redox potential of the electrode.

Graphene or rGO typically exhibit a purely EDLC nature. However, when doped with elements like boron (B) or nitrogen (N), redox peaks appear. The introduction of small band gap energy resulting from B or N doping is the reason behind the emergence of these redox peaks.

In the case of B0.4BN superlattice, redox charge transfer occurs due to the band gap energy (as shown from the UV-vis absorbance) resulting from the stacking of rGO and h-BN layers. However, the current voltage relationship was quite different in h-BN/rGO stacked structure. The charge transfer between the electrode and electrolyte was possible at a particular potential at which the equilibrium was established between the Fermi energy of G0.4BN and the redox potential of electrolyte.

Alternatively, another explanation for the presence of redox peaks can be attributed to the interaction between a Lewis acid and a Lewis base.[52,53] The molecular structure of h-BN closely resembles that of graphene, yet there is a disparity in electronegativity between the elements boron (B) and nitrogen (N). Consequently, the B center acts as a Lewis acid, leading to alterations in the oxidation states of both B and N during the charging and discharging processes. When immersed in a KOH electrolyte, the hydroxide ions (OH⁻) assume the role of Lewis bases and chemically adsorb onto the surfaces of B. This adsorption process is completely reversible and serves as the underlying cause of the redox peaks observed in h-BN. In the context of an h-BN/rGO stacked structure, the differences in electronegativity among carbon (C), nitrogen (N), and boron (B) facilitate the reversible adsorption of the Lewis base (OH⁻) onto the surfaces of the Lewis acids (B and C).

To ensure the contribution of the double layer capacitance (Cdl), the CV of all the sample was examine and represented in the **Figure S6**. CV was carried out within the potential window of 0 to 0.5 V. G0.4BN, G0.8BN, and rGO shows perfect rectangular nature which is the fingerprint of Cdl or EDLC. On the other hand, G0BN shows distorted CV nature due to the poor electrochemically active h-BN. In situations where the primary focus is on the involvement of interfacial charges on the electrode, the crucial factor for electrochemical charge storage lies in attaining electrostatic adsorption and desorption within an appropriate potential range. This phenomenon gains particular importance when utilizing electrode materials such as graphene or reduced graphene oxide (rGO), which boast a wealth of π -electrons. However, the introduction of a band gap brings about the creation of a space charge region within the electrode materials, which significantly affects the overall process. **Figure S7 (a-d)** shows the variation of CV nature with scan rates. For pure h-BN, CV nature is distorted and current response did not increase with scan rate, due to the absence of graphene. On the other hand, due to the contribution of double layer formed on graphene surface G0.4BN, G0.8BN, and rGO show quite rectangular CV nature at the higher scan rates. At the same time, current response increased significantly with increasing scan rate.

The investigation focused on understanding the effect of the presence of graphene in the samples. This was analyzed by examining the power law relationship between current (i) and scan rate (v), represented by the equation: $i = av^b$, where appropriate values were assigned to variables a and b . [54,55] A value of b close to 0.5 indicates a diffusion-controlled relationship between i and v , suggesting a redox charge storage mechanism of the electrode. Conversely, a value of b close to 1 suggests the double layer capacitance. The measurement of b , obtained from the slope of the \log

(i) versus $\log(v)$ plot (**Figure S8**), was determined to be 0.41, 0.79, 0.91, and 0.92 for G0BN (pure h-BN), G0.4BN (2D stacking of h-BN/rGO), G0.8BN (B, N-doped rGO), and rGO, respectively. The calculated b -values indicated that pure h-BN don't support the formation of CdI on the electrode surface. On the other hand, pure graphene (rGO) and B, N-doped rGO, both possess a b -value close to 1, which ensured the formation of CdI. Interestingly, the b -value of stacked h-BN/rGO structure is slightly lower than pure rGO, but significantly higher than pure h-BN. This scenario suggested that due to the presence of stacked rGO layers G0.4BN was benefited from the formation of CdI on the electrode surface.

Figure 3 Calculation of active electrochemical site (voltametric charge/ q^*), (a) outer surface voltametric charge (q^* out) calculated as extrapolation of q^* to $v = \infty$ from the q^* vs $1/v^{1/2}$ plot, (b) inner surface voltametric charge (q^* in) calculated as extrapolation of q^* to $v = 0$ from the $1/q^*$ vs the $v^{1/2}$ plot, (c), EIS, and (d) Tafel polarization plot of G0BN, G0.4BN, and G0.8BN, respectively.

For an efficient catalyst, surface adsorption properties play a crucial role in its reaction kinetics. The surface adsorption property can be estimated from the electrochemically active surface area or the amount of voltametric charge (q^*) of the sample.[56,57] The outer surface voltametric charge (q^* out) and the inner surface voltametric charge (q^* in) were calculated from the extrapolation of q^* to $v = 0$ and $v = \infty$, (where v is the scan rate) respectively (**Figures 3a and 3b**).

The q^*_{out} was calculated as 0.3, 3.7, and 2.6 mC/cm^2 for G0BN, G0.4BN, and G0.8BN, respectively. On the other hand, q^*_{in} was calculated as 3.3, 43.5, and 31.8 mC/cm^2 for G0BN, G0.4BN, and G0.8BN, respectively. It is interesting to notice that for the 2D samples, the amount of voltametric charge is almost ten times higher than the pure h-BN. At the same time, the electrochemically active surface of 2D stacked graphene/h-BN was much higher in comparison to the B, N-doped graphene. The availability of abundant interfaces due to the stacking of two different 2D structures enhanced the accessibility of the electrochemical active sites for G0.4BN.

The number of hydrogen adsorbed on the electrode surface depends on the amount of active sites. On the other hand, the amount of active sites can be estimated from the voltametric charge. The absorbance of hydrogen or electrolyte ions only occur on the outer surface of the electrode materials. Thus, if the total voltametric charge (q^*) is the summation of outer (q^*_{out}) and inner (q^*_{in}) voltametric charge, then adsorption amount will increase with the increasing q^*_{out} value. The active sites were calculated from the using the following relation, Number of active sites = $q^*_{out} / 1.60217662 \times 10^{-19}$ coulombs.[58,59] Following the relation, number of active sites of G0BN (pure h-BN), G0.4BN (h-BN/rGO stacked structure), and G0.8BN (B,N-doped rGO) were calculated as 1.8×10^{18} , 23×10^{18} , and 16×10^{18} , respectively. Estimated q^*_{in} , q^*_{out} , and number of active sites of G0BN, G0.4BN, and G0.8BN were compared in the **Figure S9**. Thus, it can be concluded that the hydrogen adsorption increased significantly for h-BN/rGO stacking, in comparison to pure h-BN, and B, N doped rGO.

In order to understand the effect of microstructure on the charge transfer at the electrode-electrolyte interfaces, the EIS analysis was carried out. **Figure 3c** shows the Nyquist plot of EIS results. Pure h-BN, B, N-doped graphene, and h-BN/graphene stacked structures show completely different impedance profiles. At first, pure h-BN shows a long Warburg tail due to its low electrical conductivity and lack of porosity, while graphene-containing samples possess a short Warburg tail. Another important thing was noticed: the h-BN/graphene stacking resulted in an inclined nature to the low frequency region, whereas the other samples (G0BN and G0.8BN) have a steeper low frequency region. For in-depth analysis, all the EIS was fitted with ZView software and represented in **Figure S10–S12** of the supporting information. Among the different impedance parameters, the most important element is the charge transfer resistance (R_p).[60,61] For fast kinetics and efficient water splitting, the catalyst should possess a low R_p in an alkaline electrolyte.[62] Here, the R_p was calculated as 771, 10, and 32 ohm for G0BN, G0.4BN, and G0.8BN, respectively. As discussed from the voltametric study, due to the availability of larger active sites resulting from the abundant interfaces of the 2D h-BN/graphene stacked structure, low R_p was generated at the electrode-electrolyte interfaces.[63] Another interesting thing to be noticed is that, the low frequency region of both the G0BN and G0.8BN was fitted with Warburg elements, whereas constant phase element (CPE) was required to fit the G0.4BN. CPE represents the inhomogeneity of the electrode surface.[64] Due to the presence of two different 2D layers, inhomogeneity was created on the G0.4BN surface. Thus, G0.4BN benefited from the presence of graphene by providing high double layer capacitance (C_{dl}). At the same time, due to its stacked structure, G0.4BN possesses low charge transfer resistance in the alkaline electrolyte. The electrode kinetics were further investigated from polarization Tafel plots (**Figure 3d**). The Tafel slope was calculated by fitting the anodic and cathodic regions of the polarization plots (**Figures S13, S14, and S15** for G0BN, G0.4BN, and G0.8BN, respectively). Non-conducting pure h-BN shows a large anodic and cathodic Tafel slope (~ 120 mV/dec) due to the large charge transfer resistance. On the other hand, G0.4BN possesses very low anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes of 18 and 19 mV/dec, due to the low

charge transfer resistance as a result of abundant interfaces at graphene/h-BN stacking. Although the Tafel slopes of G0.8BN (29 and 25 mV/dec for anodic and cathodic slope) are significantly lower in comparison to those of pure h-BN, they are comparatively larger than G0.4BN.

Figure 4 LSV plots, (a) HER polarization, (b) HER before and after stability cycles, (c) OER polarization, and (d) OER before and after stability cycles of G0BN, G0.4BN, and G0.8BN.

Water splitting or catalytic performance of the samples was compared in **Figure 4**. **Figure 4a** shows the LSV plot for the HER polarization of the samples. For pure h-BN, polarization started after -2.2 V and a large overpotential of 320 mV was required to achieve a current density of 10 mA/cm². Although polarization of B, N-doped graphene started just after 0 V, the reaction kinetic was sluggish. As a result, its polarization behaviour was not comparable to that of the traditional Pt electrode. G0.8BN needs ~72 mV overpotential to achieve 10 mA/cm² current density. Due to the structural evolution, G0.4BN exhibited fast polarization behaviour and a very small overpotential of 28 mV was sufficient to achieve 10 mA/cm² current density. **Figure 4a** shows the polarization behaviour of G0.4BN was almost identical to the traditional Pt electrode. This result completely agreed with the Tafel slope and EIS analysis. Due to the accumulation of a huge amount of adsorbed hydrogen at the interfaces, G0.4BN very low onset and overpotential.³⁷ Along with the good catalytic activity, G-BN also exhibited long-term stability. Stability was examined for 24 h, and the polarization plots are almost identical before and after the stability test (**Figure 4b**). The OER performance of the samples was compared in **Figure 4c**. Generally, OER polarization is

comparatively sluggish than the HER polarization. Thus, OER needs a much higher overpotential to achieve anodic current. It was interesting to notice that the onset potentials of OER were almost similar (~ 1.46 V) for all the samples. However, the reaction kinetics of h-BN and B, N-doped graphene, were very sluggish. To achieve a 50 mA/cm^2 current density, h-BN and B, N-doped graphene need almost 700 and 600 mV of overpotential, respectively. On the other hand, due to the unique stacked structure, G-BN acquired a 50 mA/cm^2 current density with a very small overpotential of 360 mV. At the same time, G0.4BN also exhibited long-term stability for OER activity. **Figure 4d** shows that the OER polarization plots of G0.4BN are almost similar before and after the stability test.

Figure 5 (a) Polarization curves of overall water splitting by using G0.4BN as both cathode and anode, (b) chronoamperometry plot of G0.4BN, corresponding to HER (at 100 mV overpotential), OER (at 360 mV overpotential), and overall water splitting (at 1.8 V), (c) Comparison of the EIS parameters (R_s , R_p , R_t , and C_{dl}) of G0.4BN, before and after stability test.

Due to the promising electrocatalytic activity displayed by the G0.4BN catalyst in both HER and OER, a two-electrode system was established employing G0.4BN as both the anode and cathode. The two-electrode system achieved a current density of 10 and 50 mA/cm^2 at a applied potential of 1.45 and 1.78 V (**Figure 5a**). The two-electrode system shows almost similar current-voltage profile (a current density of 10 and 50 mA/cm^2 at a applied potential of 1.48 and 1.83 V) after 24 h stability test (**Figure 5b**). We are thankful to you for the valuable suggestion. **Figure 5b**

represents the chronoamperometry (at constant potential) of the HER, OER, and overall water splitting. Chronoamperometry of HER was carried out at a constant overpotential of 360 mV. The initial current was 49.7 mA/cm² and after 24h current was recorded as 50.3 mA/cm². OER Chronoamperometry was carried out at a constant overpotential of 100 mV. The initial and final current was recorded as 51.6 and 51.2 mA/cm², respectively. In addition, chronoamperometry for overall water splitting was studied at constant potential of 1.8 V. The initial and final current was recorded as 62.8 and 61.2 mA/cm², respectively.

In order to investigate the structural stability, the SEM and TEM image of G0.4BN was captured after the chronopotentiometry (24h) test. **Figure S16a** (FE-SEM, secondary electron) ensured the presence of layered structure after 24 h chronopotentiometry. To further investigate the morphology, back scattered FE-SEM (**Figure S16b**) also captured which shows the presence of graphene/h-BN layers one upon another. TEM image (**Figure S16c**) also shows the similar sheet like structure as captured before chronopotentiometry test.

EDS analysis of G0.4BN was carried out before and after the chronopotentiometry test. **Figure S17** (a-c) shows the SEM images and corresponding EDS plots of G0.4BN before chronopotentiometry test. EDS was taken corresponding to the point p1 and p2. The EDS results were shown in the **Figure S18** (a & b). The stoichiometry of B:C:N was 1:2.2:1.2, and 1:2.1:1.2 corresponding to the point p1 and p2, respectively. EDS results suggested that At% of B and N are almost similar, where C percentage is almost double than B and N. The EDS results supported the formation of h-BN/graphene stacked structures. The low oxygen content suggested the reduction of GO during annealing process. **Figure S17** (d-f) shows the SEM images and corresponding EDS plots of G0.4BN after chronopotentiometry test. EDS was taken corresponding to the point p3 and p4. The EDS results were shown in the **Figure S18** (c & d). The stoichiometry of B:C:N was 1:2.1:1.2, and 1:2.1:1.2 corresponding to the point p3 and p4, respectively. EDS results shows that the composition of G0.4BN remain unaltered after the chronopotentiometry test. Only difference was noticed that oxygen content increased a little after chronopotentiometry test.

The effect of the long chronopotentiometry test on the microstructure of the electrode can also be investigated by EIS analysis. **Figure S11 and S19** shows the EIS plot of G0.4BN before and after chronopotentiometry test. The EIS results were analyzed by ZView software. The EIS analysis drawn the similar conclusion like EDS results, that no significant change was noticed after chronopotentiometry test. No significant change in the series resistance (R_s), charge transfer resistance (R_p and R_t), and C_{dl} was noticed after the chronopotentiometry test (**Figure 5d**). EIS analysis further agreed with the EDS results that the microstructure and composition G0.4BN remain unaffected after 24 h stability test.

4. Conclusions

In summary, 2D stacking of graphene and h-BN was employed for the overall water splitting electrode. The presence of the h-BN layer within graphene not only enhanced the active surface area but also increased the hydrogen adsorption on the electrode surface. At the same time, the stacking of h-BN did not affect the electrical conductivity of graphene. As a result, the graphene/h-BN stacked structure achieved a very low overpotential of 28 mV (for 10 mA/cm² current density) for hydrogen evolution. At the same time, a significantly low overpotential of 360 mV (for 50 mA/cm² current density) was realized for oxygen evolution. Due to the modified structure,

graphene/h-BN shows very low Tafel slopes (29 and 25 mV/dec for anodic and cathodic slope, respectively), confirming fast reaction kinetics. At the same time, the long-term stability of the 2D stacked graphene/h-BN structure ensured its potential application for overall water splitting by maximizing the electrochemical performance.

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